

RESEARCH ARTICLE | OPEN ACCESS**Talent Management and Organizational Performance in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island****Ekure, Vincent Ovuakporien^{1*} & Prof. Chris C. Orga²**^{1,2}*Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu****Corresponding Author****Background**

Workers are the lubricants that stimulate the oil and gas industries in Nigeria through the applications of their talents in off-shore and on-shore operations. From the foregoing, human resource management scholars attest that talent management is the key to the survivability and sustainability of every firm (Ahmadi, Ahmadi, & Abbaspalangi, 2012). It has been shown that talent management influences the performance of employees positively in many firms especially when the firm attracts, develops, and retains potential talents (Mangusho, Murei, & Nelima, 2015). Scholars such as Onwuka, Ugwu, and Kekeocha (2015) accentuate that; as a result of talent scarcity, most firms around the globe are in serious competition to attract potential talents quite apart from retaining them so as to overtake their rivals in terms of service and profitability. Talent

management in the oil and gas industry is driven by a shortage of relevant skills such as pipeline electronic security systems, offshore electronic monitoring systems, and computerized drilling mechanisms.

However, since the oil and gas industry contribute majorly to Nigeria's economic growth, attracting potential talents becomes crucial to their survival and sustainability. It is for this reason that the Federal Government of Nigeria in the year 2000 introduced the local content policy which was aimed at bridging the talent gaps between foreign firms and indigenous firms (Ocheni, 2015). Talents are usually attracted through the formal recruitment process which translates to selection and placement. The second phase of talent management is talent development which is training attracted talents in areas that they are not familiar with or are needed urgently by the firm. This is usually done by either on-the-job training or off-the-job training. Once they have been developed, firms are expected to

ABSTRACT

The study examined the relationship between talent management and organizational performance in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island. Specifically, the study examined the relationship between recruitment/selection and profitability, the relationship between training/development and employee productivity, and the relationship between career development and customer satisfaction in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island. The research employed a survey research design. The population of this study consisted of all 287 management and top senior staff of the seven departments in Light LNG, Bonny Island. Since the population is not large, the entire population completed a structured questionnaire. The result showed that there was a significant positive relationship between recruitment/selection and profitability there was a significant positive relationship between training/development and employee productivity; there was a significant positive relationship between career development and customer satisfaction in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island. The study concluded that there was a positive relationship between talent management and organizational performance in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island. It was recommended among others that organizations should pay attention to recruitment and selection of employees by designing it in such a way as to attract and employ individuals who had the right competencies and abilities that would contribute to enhancing organization performance.

Keywords: Talent Management; Organizational Performance; Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd

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roll out various compensation packages that will keep them (talent retention). It is at this stage that potential talents plan for their final career paths.

Research indicates that companies that are best at managing their talents deliver better results. The identification and development of internal high-potential employees is referred to as 'talent management within the human resource function (Nyanjom, 2013). Talent management is actions taken by organizations for the purpose of attracting, selecting, developing, and retaining the best employees in most strategic roles (Scullion & Collings, 2011). It aims at developing the right people in the right jobs at the right time, ensuring the right environment for individuals to deliver their best and remain committed to the organization. According to the Chartered Institute of Professional Development (CIPD, 2018) talent consists of those individuals who can make a difference to organizational performance either through their immediate contribution or, in the long term, by demonstrating the highest levels of potential. The growth potential of organizations globally depends on their ability to have the right personnel in the right place at the right time.

Talent management ensures that organizations have the right people with fit skills located at the right place to access business strategy (Devine, 2008). This ensures that the right employees maximize their talent for the optimal success of the organization. Talent management involves mechanisms put in place to ensure attraction, retention, and development. The employment relationship is undergoing fundamental challenges that have implications for attracting, motivating, and retention of talented employees and talent shortage has resulted in fierce competition (Nyanjom, 2013). Although talent management is a relatively new area for both the public and private sectors, most organizations have prioritized it to ensure they acquire the staff (Vito, Alagala, & Naakuu, 2018). This is because talent management has been linked to the successful attraction, retention, and development of employees (Edeh & Mlanga, 2019). The purpose of the study was to examine this link in the oil and gas industry by studying the relationship between talent management and organizational performance in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.

Statement of the Problem

Despite millions of unemployed workers, there is an acute shortage of talent. Companies still fervently search for the people who make the difference between 10 percent and 20 percent annual growth, or between profit and loss. In a knowledge-based economy, it is expected from the employees that they are capable of handling complex job responsibilities working with teams and diverse networks. The pattern of work in a knowledge-based economy is dominated by the application of modern technology. In the current business world, competitions are intense, multifaceted, complex, and widespread. This competition may be based on quality products, innovations, keeping low costs, accessing new markets or customers. Organizations can rely on their talented employees to respond to the continuous challenges of competition. This situation demands the need for talented employees to manage the functions with greater efficiency and effectiveness.

Accordingly, proper talent attraction and talent retention strategy will bring about futuristic growth in organizations. Thus, people are seen as the company's greatest asset, and through these people, the achievement of organizational goals can be facilitated. It is therefore important for organizations to attract, engage, and retain productive workers which will bring about success to the organization. Talent management dimensions like employee attraction, career path development, employee retention, succession planning, training, and development are very critical to the survival of any organization, accordingly, these dimensions aid HR managers in finding out solutions and developmental support needed for companies to succeed. This study, therefore, examined the relationship between talent management and organizational performance in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.

Objectives of the Study

The general objectives of the study were to determine the relationship between talent management and organizational performance in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.

Specific objectives include to:

- i. Examine the relationship between recruitment/selection and profitability in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.
- ii. Examine the relationship between training/development and employee productivity in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.

- iii. Examine the relationship between career development and customer satisfaction in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were postulated:

- i. There is no significant relationship between recruitment/selection and profitability in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between training/development and employee productivity in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.
- iii. There is no significant relationship between career development and customer satisfaction in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Talent Management

Talent management appeared in business and academic arenas after the publication of McKinsey's research in 1998. In this research, it is claimed that corporate America was about to be engaged in a *war* for senior executive talent that will remain a defining characteristic of their competitive landscape for decades to come (Glenn, 2012). Ever since then, organizations have started thinking about talent management. Talent management is the systematic attraction, identification, development, engagement, retention, and deployment of those individuals with high potential, and who are of particular value to an organization (Davies & Davies, 2010). Global talent management includes all organizational activities for the purpose of attracting, selecting, engaging, developing, and retaining the best employees in the most strategic roles (those roles necessary to achieve organizational strategic priorities) on a global scale (Scullion & Collings, 2011).

Thompson, Gamble, & Strickland (2005) refers to talent management as a process of attracting and integrating new employees, developing and retaining current employees, and compensating and motivating skillful personnel all with the view to achieving the aims and objectives of the organization. Therefore, employees with high potential, unique knowledge, and capacity that will bring the desired goals and success in the organization should be attracted and retained, in doing so the employee's talent must be adequately motivated to have a competitive edge in value generation to the organization. On the other hand, media firms are now developing their own employer brands by using talent management strategies to manage talented people. Subsequently, talent managers must have resourceful ideas and the capacity to deal with changes in their environment; also, existing media organizations must be abreast with modern talent management techniques in order to survive in the industry (Hiles & Bunnell, 2006). Talent management programs have impacted significantly on organizational growth due to the way most firms design and manage their organizational structure, in order to implement successful talent management, organizations need to have; a clear mission and vision, a good corporate culture, and inculcate the consciousness that talent management is of a strategic concern (Conner, 2000 and Hartley, 2004).

Talent management is important in its ability to add value to the industry even in a weak and recessive economy because it involves all the processes of planning, recruiting, developing, managing, and compensating employees in the organization. The process of hiring new talent may be very expensive when compared with the cost incurred to train, develop and retain the existing employees in the organization. Organizations in their quest to grow have seen the need for talent management programs and as such are currently embarking on intensive talent retention programs in their organization. Talent retention programs at the first instance may look expensive in the short run due to increases in wages, rewards, and compensation but the organization will be of competitive advantage in the long run. Armstrong (2006) suggested that research on talent integration has shown organizations consistency in talent recruitment, selection, engagement, and management, which has given some organizations a competitive advantage. Organizations need to standardize best labor practices and implement a good talent management culture. In the same vein, Laff (2006) argued that the main force in implementing successful talent management culture in any organization is the total commitment from the employer and employees to achieve the firm's corporate intent.

Dimensions of Talent Management

Scholars such as (Anwar, Nisar, Khan, & Sana, 2014) identified talent identification, talent development, and talent engagement as indicators of talent management. Varying the above indicators (Koltapeh, Forotageh, Afruz, & Hossein, 2015; Oladapo, 2014) identifies talent attraction, talent development, and talent retention. In another development, Hamidi, Saberi, and Safari (2014) pointed out talent identification, talent selection, talent utilization, and talent development. But Beheshtifar, Nasab, and Moghadam (2012) came up with talent attraction, talent evaluation, talent development, and talent retention. Nonetheless, Chitsaz-Isfahani and Boustani (2014) established job experience, coaching, mentoring, training, succession planning, and career management as a dimension of talent management. This study however focuses on talent attraction, talent development, and talent retention as dimensions of talent management.

Talent Attraction

Armstrong and Taylor (2014) affirmed that talent attraction covers recruitment, selection, employer branding, and employee value proposition. It is expected that organizations take initiatives to attract talent as the number of talents in the labor market is limited (Athey, 2008). Thus, attracting talent has become a challenge as well. Employer branding can be a good way of attracting talent to the organization. It is a systematic way of presenting an organization with the intention of making it distinctive from others for potential and current employees. Employer branding is the sum of all efforts from the company to communicate to existing and prospective staff that it is the desirable place to work (Lloyd, 2002). Chhabra and Sharma (2014) find positive relationships between the employer brand and the likelihood of applying. The image of the organization is created by the effects of good corporate citizenship, progressive labor practices, an emphasis on diversity, sponsorship of cultural activities, and pro-environmental practices (Smith, Bauer, & Cable, 2001). Lemmink, Schuijff, and Streukens (2003) find that corporate image and company employment image have a significant effect on the intentions of applicants.

Boxall and Purcell (2003) argue that firms need to attract and nurture people who have the competencies and abilities that will contribute to enhancing organizational performance. Katou and Budhwar (2007) studying the effect of HRM policies on organization performance in Greek manufacturing firms found that the relationship between recruitment and performance is positive. Furthermore, Aposporia, Nikandroua, Brewster, and Papalexandrisa (2008) in their study on HRM and organizational performance in northern and southern Europe have also found that recruitment is positively related to organizational performance.

Talent Development

Employee development is an ongoing process of assisting employees on how to perform the work. It is one of the significant functions of Human Resource Management as employees are critical to organizations' success (Ferris, Hochwarter, Buckley, Harrell-Cook & Frink, 1999). Employee development is an integrated set of planned programs designed to assure that all individuals have the competence necessary to perform to their fullest potential in support of the organization's goal (Jacobs & Washington, 2003). Employee development activities include off-the-job and on-the-job training programs, educational programs and seminars, job rotations, self-study materials and mentoring programs (Jacobs & Washington, 2003). (Noe, 2016) affirmed that development is concerned with formal education, experiences on the job, relationships, and assessments of personality as well as abilities that help workers perform effectively in their current or future job and enterprises. He admitted that development activities help firms reduce employee turnover by showing them that the firm is investing in their skill development and enhancing managers' skills that can create a conducive work environment that makes workers want to come to work and contribute to firm goals. Chand and Katou (2007) have found training & development is positively related to organizational performance.

Talent Retention

Employee retention is the systematic technique applied by management to help employees stay for a longer period of time (Tephillah & Swamalatha, 2015). Irshad (2007) has identified some important HR practices that can influence the retention of employees in the organization. First, organizational culture plays a crucial role in retaining employees in the organization. Second, family and flexible time options can also be considered important factors for employee retention. Third, compensation and recognition are considered as motivation to employees which leads to their retention in the firm. Fourth, career development and promotion opportunities drive retention. A

survey conducted by CIPD (2018) revealed that firms retain talented employees by; improving pay by 50 percent; increasing learning and development opportunities by 49 percent; improving line management people skills by 45 percent; improving selection techniques by 40 percent; improving induction process by 39 percent; improving employee involvement by 38 percent; improving benefits by 38 percent; and improving work-life balance by 36 percent.

Organizational Performance

Performance has been alluded to as action-oriented, the results that yield from this action, and the successes accomplished in comparison to competitors (Corvellec, 1994). Organizational performance can be measured using both financial and non-financial indicators (Tseng, 2014). As classified by Maltz, Shenhar, & Reilly (2003), there are five key factors utilized for the assessment of performance, which are financial, market/customer, people development, process, and the future. With respect to Richard, Devinney, & Yip (2009), the approaches that are observed, measured, and evaluated are the financial, product market, and shareholder outcomes; these approaches are evaluated to study the performance of an organization and the attainment of its goals and objectives. Nevertheless, Dyer and Reeves (1995), classified three different results for organizational performance, which are financial results (profit and market share); organizational results (efficiency, quality, and productivity); and human resources results (satisfaction, attitudes and behaviors, and commitment). Aposporia et al. (2008) applied productivity and profitability to measure performance and; Katou and Budhwar (2007) used operational measures such as effectiveness, efficiency, development, quality, and innovation. Chand and Katou (2007) used sales growth, productivity, profitability, goal achievement, and good services; and Ngo et al. (1998) used sales, net profit, and development of new products/services to measure performance in their studies.

Theoretical Framework

The theory relevant to this study is the social cognitive career theory.

The Social Cognitive Career Theory

The social cognitive career theory was conceptualized as a derivative of Bandura's general social cognitive theory in which the intersection of intrinsic and extrinsic factors influences psychosocial learning. This theory has been termed as the most promising career theory that may prove satisfactory in retention and career development. Lent and Brown (2006) expanded the scope of social cognitive career theory, offering a new and related social – cognitive model designed to explain the ways in which previously identified inputs such as self-efficacy and outcome expectations, along with person and contextual variables are related to job satisfaction. The authors cited recent research (Heller, Watson & Lies, 2004), that linked job satisfaction to overall subjective well-being, thus providing a rationale for the use of the theory in the current research. The primary focus is on the central elements of social cognitive namely: self-efficacy and outcome expectations. Self-efficacy can be defined as an individual's sense of control and responsibility for his/her personal environment. It is also defined as the beliefs in one's capability to organize and execute the courses of action required to produce given attainments. Self-efficacy is concerned with the belief in the ability to exercise control over one's actions and events that affect lives.

Beliefs impact life choices, motivation, quality of actions and the ability to overcome adversity. The sources of self-efficacy are derived from three sources: mastery experience, vicarious experience and social persuasion. Vicarious experience is observing the model of someone similar managing a task successfully and drawing experience. Outcome expectations refer to the personal belief that successfully performing certain tasks may result in probable response outcomes.

Lent *et al.* (2006) expanded upon Bandura's work to focus exclusively on the development of the individual within the context of career. Managers who wish to retain talent can borrow heavily from this theory. Career behavior is driven by self-efficacy or the belief in the ability to accomplish something worthwhile. The degree of achievement depends on two factors: outcome expectations or the idea that initiating a particular behavior will yield the desired results and goals. If a person feels confident of his/her abilities, he/she is more likely to take specific actions to reach them. This is especially so for the young generation of employees popularly known as the millennials. They have grown up with an abundance of role models from parents and other mentors and still expect the same at work.

This theory associates individual failure to insufficient skill and knowledge which are deemed as acquirable. It is therefore imperative to provide customized training and development opportunities to the employees. This theory is relevant to the current study in that career behavior is driven by self-efficacy or belief in the ability to accomplish something worthwhile. The degree of achievement depends on two factors; outcome expectations or the idea that initiating a particular behavior will yield to desired results. Goals are keys because if a person feels confident of his/her abilities, he's more likely to take specific actions to reach them. If employees feel supported and their goals and career advancement looked into, their intention to stay will be higher.

Empirical Review

Adeyemi, Dumade, & Fadare (2020) studied the influence of recruitment and selection on organizational performance. The purpose of this study was to assess the impact of recruitment and selection on organizational performance. The study obtained information from twenty (20) respondents from the staff of Access Bank, odogunyan branch through the use of a questionnaire. The results indicated that advertising job vacancies to the general public, use of employment agent(s), and employee referrals are mostly the mode for recruiting potential employees, it was also realized that the method used in the recruitment and selection process was very effective and equally helped improve employee performance. The study revealed that the selection and recruitment process is also characterized by lots of challenges. Among the recommendations made were that potential employees should all be treated fairly in the recruitment and selection process, and more so employees must be appraised constantly to ensure that they improve upon their performance.

Matolo, Iravo, and Waitutu (2019) studied the relationship between recruitment and selection and employee performance in Technical Training Institutes in Kenya. The objective was to find out the relationship between recruitment and selection, and employee performance in technical training institutes in Kenya. The research adopted both descriptive and correlational research designs and a mixture of an approach consisting of both qualitative and quantitative research methods. A sample size of three Technical Institutes in Kenya and comprising 137 respondents was used. A linear regression analysis was used to explain the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. The data was analyzed and presented using statistical methods including them tables, bar graphs, and pie charts. The results were used to test and determine the relationship of the variables. The findings revealed that employee welfare and reward management had the greatest effect on performance. The findings of the research were that there was a significant positive relationship between recruitment and selection and employee performance.

Sandamali, et al. (2018) studied the Relationship between Training and Development and Employee Performance of Executive Level Employees in Apparel Organizations. This study attempts to identify the relationship between training and development and employee performance of executive-level employees of Apparel organizations in Si Lanka. The study was quantitative and a cross-sectional survey where data was collected through a structured questionnaire. A simple random sampling technique was applied to select the sample and the sample consisted of 150 executive-level employees. The data were analyzed using correlation and regression analytical tools. Findings revealed that training and development are positively related to employee performance of executive-level employees. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended that the organization should build a correct and logically substantial mechanism to select the employees who definitely participate in the training program and the organization management should establish a widely spread post-evaluation scheme to evaluate the performance of employees.

Kum & Karodia (2014) studied the Impact of Training and Development on Employee Performance: a case study of ESCON Consulting. The study focuses on the impact of training and development on employee performance at ESCON. A random sampling method was used to select participants for this study, which adopted a quantitative approach. Accordingly, data were collected using a questionnaire. The study was limited to employees of ESCON. Subsequently, the findings revealed that working conditions and a lack of resources affect the training and development of employees. It is recommended that certain areas be improved, that is, management support, the provision of feedback to employees, and the conducting of employee training on a continuous basis. The findings show that this would improve employee performance in the organization.

Nasution, Mariatin, & Zahreni (2018). The Influence of Career Development and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance. The objective of this research was to examine the influence of career development and organizational culture on employee performance. The research used a quantitative approach which involved 242 permanent

employees of Bank Pembangunan Daerah. The result of statistical analysis showed that career development and organizational culture have a positive and significant influence on employee performance. The implication of this research is expected to be able to help the company's management increase their employees' performance by carrying out objective, transparent, and fair career development programs and strengthen organizational culture by socializing and monitoring the implementation of firm values.

Ntadom, Atueyi, & Jacobs (2021) studied the effect of Career Development on Organizational Performance: A Study of selected higher institutions in Anambra State Nigeria. The study examined the effect of career development on organizational performance, a Study of selected higher institutions in Anambra State Nigeria. The study was anchored on the Self-concept theory of career development. As a cross-sectional survey research design was used, a structured questionnaire instrument was developed and used for data collection by the researcher which reflected such options as strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree, which is popularly referred to as five (5) points Likert scale. It was used to obtain information from the respondents. The population of the study comprised 57, 710 students selected across the five southeastern states of Nigeria. A sample size of 399 students was drawn from the population, using the Taro Yamane formula of which three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaires were duly completed and returned; showing a 96% response rate. Research hypotheses were tested using ANOVA regression analysis which was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for social science (SPSS) version 23. The study found that career development has a significant effect on Organizational Performance.

Methodology

A survey research design was adopted for the study. A primary source of data was adopted for the study. A structured questionnaire was used to generate data. The method of questioning used is the semantic differential type such as: Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The population of this study consisted of all 287 management and top senior staff of the seven departments in Light LNG, Bonny Island. The data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (rs) used to analyze the hypotheses with the aid of a statistical package for social sciences (SPSS 20.0).

Results

Questionnaire Response Rate

The questionnaire was distributed to 287 respondents, out of which 240 returned, representing a response rate of 83%. The response rate table is given below.

Table 1: Questionnaire Response Rate

Respondents	Distributed	Returned	% Returned	Not Returned	% Not Returned
	287	240	83	47	17

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Analysis of Biographic Data

Table 2: Distribution of Gender of Respondents

Gender	Response	% response
Male	150	62
Female	90	38
Total	240	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 2 showed that 150 respondents (62%) are male, while 90 (38%) are female.

Table 3 Distribution of Age Bracket of respondents

Age Bracket	Response	% Response
30 and under	10	4
31 - 40 years	98	41
41 - 50years	90	38
51 -60 years	24	10
61 years and above	18	7
Total	240	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 3 showed that 10 (4) respondents were 30 years and under, 98 (41%) are between 31 – 40 years, 90 (38%) are between 41 – 50 years, 24 (10%) are between 51 – 60 years while 18 (7%) are 61 years and above.

Table 4 Distribution of Educational Qualification of respondents

Educational Qualification	Response	% Response
HND/BSC	20	8
M.Sc /MBA	180	75
PhD/DBA	40	17
Total	240	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 4 showed that 20 (8%) have HND/B.SC certificate, 180 (75%) have M.Sc/MBA, while 40 (17%) PhD/DBA certificates.

Table 5 Distribution of Length of service of respondents

Length of service	Response	% Response
0-5 years	10	4
6-10 years	40	17
11 - 15 years	70	29
16 -20 years	90	38
21 – 25 years	20	8
26 – 30 years	10	4
Total	240	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 5 showed that 5 respondents (4%) have worked between 0 - 5 years, 20 (17%) are between 6 - 10 years, 35 (29%) are between 11– 15 years, 45 (38%) are between 16 – 20 years, 10 (8%) between 21 – 25 years while 5 (4) have worked for between 26 – 30 years.

Data Analyses

The relationship between recruitment/selection and profitability in Light Liquified Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island

Table 6: Relationship between recruitment/selection and profitability

OPTIONS	RESPONSES	%
STRONGLY AGREE	90	38
AGREE	110	46
UNDECIDED	10	4
DISAGREE	20	8
STRONGLY DISAGREE	10	4
TOTAL	240	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 6 showed that 90 respondents (38%) strongly agreed that there is a relationship between recruitment/selection and profitability in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island, 110 (46%) agreed; 10 (4%) were undecided; 20 (8%) disagreed; while 10 (4%) strongly disagreed. Since more than 50 percent agreed, it showed that there is a relationship between recruitment/selection and profitability in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island

The relationship between training/development and employee productivity in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.

Table 7 Relationship between training/development and employee productivity

Options	Responses	% Responses
Strongly Agree	100	42
Agree	90	38
Undecided	20	8
Disagree	20	8
Strongly Disagree	10	4
TOTAL	240	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 7 showed that 100 respondents (42%) strongly agreed that there is a relationship between training/development and employee productivity in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island, 90 (38%) agreed; 20 (8%) were undecided; 20 (8%) disagreed, while 10 (4%) strongly disagreed. Since more than 50 percent agreed, it showed that there is a relationship between training/development and employee productivity in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island

The relationship between career development and customer satisfaction in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island

Table 8 Relationship between career development and customer satisfaction

Options	Responses	% Responses
Strongly Agree	100	42
Agree	90	38
Undecided	20	8
Disagree	20	8
Strongly Disagree	10	4
TOTAL	240	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 8 showed that 100 respondents (42%) strongly agreed that there is a relationship between career development and customer satisfaction in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island, 90 (38%) agreed; 20 (8%) were undecided; 20 (8%) disagreed, while 10 (4%) strongly disagreed. Since more than 50 percent agreed, it showed that there is a relationship between career development and customer satisfaction in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between recruitment/selection and profitability in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island

Table 9 Correlation between Recruitment/Selection and Profitability

		<i>Recruitment</i>	<i>Profitability</i>
Recruitment/Selection	Pearson Cor	1	.770**
	Sig (2-tailed)	.214	.000
	N	240	240
Profitability	Pearson Cor	.770**	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	240	240

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 9 above shows the result of a bivariate analysis between Recruitment/Selection and Profitability. From the table, Recruitment/Selection has a positive significant relationship with Profitability with a high correlation coefficient of .770 and a p-value of .000. Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected, and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between training/development and employee productivity in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island

Table 10: Correlation between training/development and employee productivity

		<i>Training/Dev</i>	<i>Employee Productivity</i>
Training/development	Pearson Cor	1	.828**
	Sig (2-tailed)	.214	.000
	N	240	240
Employee Productivity	Pearson Cor	.828**	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	240	240

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 10 above shows the result of a bivariate analysis between training/development and employee productivity. From the table, training/development has a positive significant relationship with employee productivity with a high correlation coefficient of .828 and a p-value of .000. Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected, and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between career development and customer satisfaction in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.

Table 11: Correlation between career development and customer satisfaction

		<i>Career Development</i>	<i>Customer Satisfaction</i>
Career Development	Pearson Cor	1	.768**
	Sig (2-tailed)	.214	.000
	N	240	240
Customer Satisfaction	Pearson Cor	.768**	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	240	240

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 11 above shows the result of a bivariate analysis between career development and customer satisfaction. From the table, career development has a positive significant relationship with customer satisfaction with a high

correlation coefficient of .768 and a p-value of .000. Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected, and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion of the Findings

This study has been designed to investigate the relationship between talent management and organizational performance. The components of talent management (Recruitment and selection; training/development; and career development) have a positive relationship with measures of organizational performance (Profitability; employee productivity; and customer satisfaction). The positive relationships between Recruitment and selection; training/development; and career development and measures of organizational performance are consistent with previous research conducted to investigate such relations (Anwar, et al., 2014; Sandamali, et al., 2018; Matolo, et al., 2019). The implication of the result of this study is that organizations can look into the area of talent management to achieve the desired performance for the organization.

Summary of Findings

From the analyses, the following findings were made:

- i. There was a significant positive relationship between recruitment/selection and profitability in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island
- ii. There was a significant positive relationship between training/development and employee productivity in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island
- iii. There was a significant positive relationship between career development and customer satisfaction in Light Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island

Conclusion

The study examined the relationship between talent management and organizational performance. The study found a positive relation between variables of talent management like recruitment and selection, talent development strategies such as training and development, and talent retention strategies like career development, and variables of organizational performance such as profitability, employee productivity, and customer satisfaction. The study, therefore, concluded that there is a positive relationship between talent management and organizational performance in Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, Bonny Island.

Recommendations

From the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Organizations should pay attention to recruitment and selection of employees by designing it in such a way as to attract and employ individuals who have the right competencies and abilities that will contribute to enhancing organization performance.
- ii. Employee development efforts in the form of training and development should be a continuous exercise to ensure that organizations have employees with the right skill and competence necessary to perform to their fullest potential to ensure high performance for the organization.
- iii. Retention efforts such as career development and promotion opportunities should be intensified by organizations to help the best available talents stay for a longer period of time and contribute to organizational performance efforts

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